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POSTER PRESENTATIONS

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REPURPOSED DRUG COMBINATIONS THAT EFFICACIOUSLY INHIBIT FIBROSARCOMA INDUCED BY BHK-21/C13 IN HAMSTERS

Dušica J. Popović¹, Kosta J. Popović², Dejan Miljković³, Dušan Lalošević⁴,
Zana Dolićanin⁵, Ivan Čapo⁶ and Jovan K. Popović^{7*}

¹State University of Novi Pazar, Novi Pazar, Republic of Serbia

dusicapopovic@np.ac.rs

²Faculty of Medicine, University of Novi Sad, Novi Sad, Republic of Serbia

kosta.popovic@mf.uns.ac.rs

³Faculty of Medicine, University of Novi Sad, Novi Sad, Republic of Serbia

dejan.miljkovic@mf.uns.ac.rs

⁴Faculty of Medicine, University of Novi Sad, Novi Sad, Republic of Serbia

dusan.lalosevic@mf.uns.ac.rs

⁵State University of Novi Pazar, Novi Pazar, Republic of Serbia

zdolicanin@np.ac.rs

⁶Faculty of Medicine, University of Novi Sad, Novi Sad, Republic of Serbia

ivan.capo@mf.uns.ac.rs

^{7*}Faculty of Medicine, University of Novi Sad, Novi Sad, Republic of Serbia

Corresponding author: **jovapopmf@gmail.com; jovan.popovic@mf.uns.ac.rs*

Introduction: A large diversity in molecular mechanisms of cancer regulation allows some marketed pleiotropic non-oncological non-toxic pharmaceuticals to be used in oncology, what reduce duration and cost of novel anticancer treatment research. By docking data of biomolecular activities of nontoxic non-oncological drugs with anticancer targets, we have chosen some promising combinations for further screening on fibrosarcoma in hamsters and separated combinations for possible use in oncology. For each repurposed drug – component of efficacious combination, identification of known anticancer mechanisms was found in the literature and jointly compared.

Materials and methods: Syrian golden hamsters of both sexes, weighing approximately 70 g, were randomly allocated to control and experimental groups, with 6 animals per group. In all groups, 2×10^6 BHK-21/C13 cells in 1 ml were injected subcutaneously into the animals' backs. Peroral treatments were carried out with metformin, caffeine, deoxycholic acid, 2-Deoxy-D-glucose, itraconazole, nitroglycerin, disulfiram, mebendazole and their selected combinations.

In the course of experiment, tumor volumes were calculated using 3 diameters. The tumor diameters and the tumor burdens were evaluated daily using calipers and the following ellipsoid volume formula: $\text{volume} = 4\pi abc/3$, where a, b and c are half-diameters. After 2-3 weeks, when the tumors were approximately 2-3 cm in the control group, all animals were sacrificed. After sacrifice, blood samples were collected for hematological and biochemical analyses and main organs toxicologically analyzed. The tumors were excised and weighed, their diameters were exactly measured, and the exact tumor volume was determined using the standard water volume displacement

method. The tumor samples were pathohistologically and immunohistochemically assessed.

Results: This study showed that two-drug combinations: metformin with caffeine, metformin with deoxycholic acid, metformin with 2-Deoxy-D-glucose, metformin with itraconazole, metformin with nitroglycerin and metformin with disulfiram can significantly ($P < 0.05$) suppress fibrosarcoma development in hamsters with doses equivalent to oncological human doses, without toxicity and influence on biochemical and hematological tests.

Figure: Tumor density, surface area, surface/volume ratio and Ki-67 positivity among the treated groups of animals. **C** - control, **M** - treated with metformin, **I** - treated with itraconazole, **M+I** - treated with the combination of metformin and itraconazole.

* $P < 0.05$, statistically significant compared to control (**C**) and single treatments (**M**, **I**).

Conclusions: For significant cancer inhibitory effect, combination of two investigated drugs must be used and at least one drug in combined treatment must possess NF-kB antagonistic activity.

All efficacious repurposed drug combinations recorded in our study on hamster fibrosarcoma might be an effective and safe approach in novel nontoxic adjuvant and relapse prevention anticancer treatment and can be recommended for further clinical trials.

Keywords: BHK-21/C13, repurposed drugs, fibrosarcoma, hamsters, NF-kB

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